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DIGITAL URBAN PLANNING

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Annotation: Digital Urban Planning is the use of digital assets and innovative approaches to urban planning. The complexity of growing cities and issues such as the housing shortage and climate change require advanced data models and the involvement of citizens and stakeholders.

Key words: digital urban planning, gis, big data, urban management, smart cities, digital cities, 3D visualization

Smart cities offer better use of space, less traffic and cleaner air, all of which increases quality of life. This makes digital urban planning and digitalization of cities inevitable. Indeed, it's already happening across many aspects of our lives, from the beginnings of the Fourth Industrial Revolution to the emergence of the Internet of Things.

Described by professor Klaus Schwab, founder and executive chairman of the World Economic Forum, this digital revolution is "characterized by a range of new technologies that are fusing the physical, digital and biological worlds, impacting all disciplines, economies and industries, and even challenging ideas about what it means to be human."³⁹

In a few words, digital urban planning is the use of digital tools, assets, and innovational approaches to urban planning. The complexity of modern cities and issues like the housing shortage and climate change, require advanced data models and techniques and the active involvement of citizens, urban planners and stakeholders.

Current urban planning and development processes are drawn out, laborious, time consuming and, at scale, prohibitively expensive. They are, typically, analog.

Let's take as an example the process for submitting a building permit. But before you can apply for that permit, you'll first need to check if any development falls within the relevant city's planning guidelines, which will include an entirely different application process with its own sets of fees and rules to adhere to.

Once planning is granted, the building permit application requires the applicant to

submit 150+ papers covering everything from multiple application forms for each relevant permit (they may be different for construction, plumbing, electricians etc) to detailed scale drawings, as well as reports on everything from energy usage to environmental impact. Once submitted, these physical papers and plans typically take three to five months to process for a decision – if everything goes smoothly (1 photo).

Smart Cities Market - Growth Rate by Region (2019 - 2024)

Apart from the obvious problems such as timescales and demand on resources can create, there are more pernicious side effects as well. Traceability of information and accountability of decision making is inevitably fractured, and that can lead to resubmitting applications at the cost of more time and money.

1 photo: World smart cities growth rate

Overall, it is an approach and process entirely incompatible with the digital ecosystem the real estate industry is heading for. But by individually digitalizing different parts of the process – assets, formats, interoperability – we will over time create a homogenous digital whole that transforms the planning and development process from the ground up.

The term "digital city" can be interpreted in various ways. On a broad scale of things, a

³⁹ <https://nomoko.world/blog/digital-urban-planning-is-key-to-creating-smart-cities/>

digital city is one where both residents and municipal authorities enjoy fast, reliable, and convenient access to an array of city-wide information services unified under the umbrella of a single digital platform. These services address a variety of aspects of everyday life and work, starting from typical e-government functions to traffic, water and energy control, waste management, surveillance, public announcements, and much more.

These services are available 24/7 and are based on various supportive technologies, such as (2 photo):

- city-wide broadband connectivity
- remote sensing (RS)
- global positioning (GPS)
- geographical information systems (GIS)
- the Internet of Things (IoT)

Aspect I	Aspect II
Physical & Social Planning	Technical & Information Planning
Function Division Spatial Pattern Physical Infrastructure Urban Land Use Construction Density	Components & Structure System Functions Information Infrastructure Spatial Database Management System

- AI/ML elements (artificial intelligence and machine learning), especially in recent years.

2 photo: Contents of Digital Urban Planning

The main purpose of all digital city initiatives is, of course, to make cities safer and more resilient to potential threats. By using predictive analysis and identifying patterns of incident occurrence, smart city platforms can substantially lower maintenance and recovery costs, and improve the quality of life of the city's residents.

Secondary, but equally important, purposes include the wider accessibility of essential information and city services, as well as economic growth through deep process optimization at all levels: city administration, public agencies, medical authorities, emergency services, businesses, and, of course, the city's residents.

But how are digital or smart cities built to be smart? What makes them different from their

conventional counterparts? As it turns out, digital urban planning is the key.

Digital urban planning is a relatively recent phenomenon, which came into being when the right technologies became widely available and affordable enough to be used on a large scale. By definition, digital urban planning is an innovative process of simulating the physical environment based on precise and up-to-date sensor-fed data in order to facilitate the decision-making process for all stakeholders.

Digital urban planning relies heavily on the concepts of digital city and digital twin, both in terms of recreating a real-life environment in the virtual space and placing the ICT infrastructure in the focus of long-term development of the actual city.

Digital urban planning heavily relies on the concept of a digital twin. Digital twins are accurate virtual representations or copies of physical objects or locations based on data coming from vast arrays of sensors, cameras, and devices monitoring the physical infrastructure. Every digital city twin in existence is a medley of underlying technologies. Generally, these are the most important technological constituents of the digital urban planning process:

- 3D visualization, including AR and VR
- Cloud-based services that aggregate, process, and store relevant data
- User-facing portals and mobile applications
- Cybersecurity tools
- IoT infrastructure capturing and feeding data to multiple destinations
- Advanced GIS services
- Big data management and analysis tools

Digital urban planning is becoming a reality for a growing number of cities around the world. Some initiatives kick off as 100% greenfield projects and have the advantage of being implemented from scratch. Some are examples of retrofitting of existing urban infrastructures to fit into the smart city paradigm.

Songdo in South Korea and Masdar in UAE are good examples of greenfield smart city projects gaining a lot of traction in the press and the industry in general. Both are young cities

that were designed and built with smart elements embedded in their DNA, with a great deal of attention placed on accessibility for all, innovative architecture, renewable energy, and the overall appeal to its residents. The fact that

all of the digital innovations were implemented in a top-to-bottom fashion ensures there are no functional bottlenecks and the entire system is scalable.

3 photo: Structure of digital urban planning Singapore

Coming from the same region, Singapore is one of the leaders of the smart city game with its outstanding Virtual Singapore program.⁴⁰ A complete digital twin of Singapore, Virtual Singapore is a massive and highly detailed 3D model of the entire city intended for residents and organizations to take an interactive 360-degree tour around the city and run experiments based on the incredible amount of detail available in the model. The platform enables users to get down to such minute details as wall materials, area of particular surfaces, sun exposure statistics, and a lot more. With these powerful tools at hand, users can simulate the effects of new construction, traffic rerouting and population growth, and instantly see how they affect the existing urban environment that they live and work in⁴¹ (3 photo).

collected by a network of low-cost sensors, enabling drivers to locate free parking spaces on the go via a mobile app. Coupled with visual surveillance data from cameras and GPS tracks from vehicles, the digital twin also aids the city administration in planning roadwork and creating crosswalks.

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